

**PHYSICO-CHEMICAL INDICATORS OF THE DEVELOPED FIRE-RETRIEVE COMPOSITIONS
BASED ON VERMICULITE AND PHOSPHORUS, NITROGEN, MAGNESIUM-CONTAINING
COMPOUND**

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Abstract

This article presents the influence of the amount of substances on the physicochemical parameters of aqueous solutions of flame retardant compositions. Solution viscosity, surface tension, density, and electrical conductivity of flame retardant compositions have been studied. Which give the choice of optimal parameters for the selection of fire retardants.

Keywords: flame retardant, viscosity, surface tension, density, electrical conductivity, composition.

Flame retardants occupy an important role in the chemical industry, from the point of view of chemical technology, there are wide opportunities for improving the production and management of them with predetermined properties and composition. The authors of works [1-4] have shown that the materials treated with fire retardants are among the necessary personal protective equipment for people in everyday life, in construction and production. The authors have studied that in the process of reducing the combustibility of materials, various compositions of flame retardants are used. In particular, intumescent flame retardants, which have the highest fire retardant efficiency, are responsible for the formation of foam coke, due to the presence of an intumescent system. The use of fire-retardant intumescent compositions is explained by the formation of a spraying in a thin layer, which has an effective fire-retardant ability and the likelihood of its application by a mechanized method on various surfaces. The advantage of intumescent flame retardants is that their appearance is similar to an ordinary solution and the likelihood of their use for the purpose of a protective and decorative coating. By increasing the temperature up to a significant threshold, the coating begins to swell, increases in size up to 2-3 times, and at the same time, a solid, protective layer of foamed coke is formed on the surface of the material. The formed foamed coke acts as a protective barrier against an open flame and protects the surface with a decrease in heat transfer [5-8].

All over the world, scientific research is being carried out to create technologies for the production of composite flame retardants for fire-resistant materials. In this regard, special attention is paid to the determination of flame retardant sorption properties on the surface, stable bonding of materials, optimal enrichment conditions, determination of effective modifying reagents, and establishment of the mechanism of impregnation of various substances on the surface of materials.

A fire retardant composition based on vermiculite was used in the work. The selected chemical substances will impart fire resistance to materials due to the presence of vermiculite and phosphorus, nitrogen, and a

magnesium-containing compound in the flame retardant composition, and the quality indicators of the material are preserved when other substances are added [9-11].

When processing cellulose-containing materials with a flame retardant suspension based on vermiculite and orthophosphoric acid, the flammability of the physically modified material decreases. The effect of the amount of added substances on the physicochemical parameters of aqueous solutions of a flame retardant composition based on vermiculite and orthophosphoric acid was studied. The quantitative indicators of glycerin in the composition on the viscosity of the solution, the value of the surface tension and the electrical conductivity of the solution, as well as the effect of the treatment process on the impregnation of materials with flame retardant compositions, were studied. The optimal composition was developed by studying the physicochemical properties of a flame retardant composition based on vermiculite dissolved with orthophosphoric acid, neutralized with alkali by dilution with water and added nitrogen-containing substances. The combustibility of the modified materials was studied by the "fire tube" method and the ignition rate was determined, it was shown that the flame retardant composition has a higher fire retardant effect, which contributes to the transfer of the combustible material to the group of hardly combustible ones. Charring, characteristic of any organic substance, is limited by the area of action of the flame. The smoke-forming ability of flame retardant compositions based on vermiculite and phosphorus for the impregnation of materials has been studied.

At present, low-molecular flame retardants are used for processing materials, which have the following disadvantages: they are easily washed off during wet processing and during chemical cleaning. In this regard, research on the creation of flame retardant compositions for materials is relevant and of great practical importance. Therefore, it is of great practical interest to reduce the combustibility of materials by using vermiculite and phosphorus-containing flame retardant compositions.

To eliminate the above shortcomings, we have developed flame retardant compositions based on aqueous solutions of vermiculite and orthophosphoric acid neutralized with alkali with the addition of a nitrogen-containing substance. Preliminary studies carried out at the Research Center of the Academy of the Ministry of Emergency Situations of the Republic of Uzbekistan showed that when the surface of materials is treated with these flame retardant compositions, their transition from the group of easily flammable to the groups of slow-burning ones is observed, which will be the object of further research. The use of vermiculite in the flame retardant composition is due to the content of silicon compounds, as well as the fact that it contains phosphorus, nitrogen, and magnesium, which slows down the combustion process.

In this paper, a method has been developed for fire protection of various materials based on cellulose using a composition of flame retardants based on vermiculite with phosphorus-containing compounds, which makes it possible to obtain materials with high fire retardant properties and improved mechanical and operational characteristics. This makes it possible to use such materials as felt mats as primary fire extinguishing agents, as well as fire-proof household products and special-purpose clothing.

Preliminary experimental studies have shown that the relative viscosity of 10% aqueous solutions of the fire retardant composition based on vermiculite and orthophosphoric acid is high, which creates significant difficulties for applying aqueous solutions of the fire retardant composition, while the material becomes rigid.

Table 1

Influence of the amount of substances on the physicochemical parameters of aqueous solutions of flame retardant composition based on vermiculite, phosphorus, nitrogen and magnesium

The composition of the composition, %		Viscosity kg/cm ² ·sec	Surface tension, N/m	Density, g/sm ³	Electrical conductivity, mk·sm/m
substances	water				
6	34	2,74	58,92	1,165	0,17
7	33	3,28	57,98	1,184	0,21
8	32	4,53	53,42	1,220	0,23
9	31	5,76	48,62	1,268	0,26
10	30	5,89	46,41	1,306	0,29
11	29	6,14	45,78	1,349	0,31
12	28	6,65	43,64	1,415	0,38

Therefore, in our studies, we used solutions of the fire retardant composition with a concentration of 6.0–12.0%. We have studied the physicochemical properties of aqueous solutions of a suspension of flame retardants based on vermiculite and orthophosphoric acid depending on the amount of glycerol (Table 1).

As can be seen from the data in Table. 1, with an increase in the amount of substances in the composition, the viscosity of the solution increases, while the value of the surface tension and electrical conductivity

of the solution decreases, which can adversely affect the treatment process when materials are impregnated with flame retardant compositions. The optimal amount of the composition is 9%.

Based on these studies, further experiments were carried out on the impregnation of materials with solutions of a flame retardant composition based on vermiculite and orthophosphoric acid in combination with alkali and water in the above composition (Table 2).

Table 2

Influence of the amount of the composition on the physicochemical parameters of aqueous solutions of flame retardant based on vermiculite and orthophosphoric acid (substance - 9.0 wt %)

The composition of the composition, %		Viscosity kg/cm ² ·sec	Surface tension, N/m	Density, g/sm ³	Electrical conductivity, mk·sm/m
Vermiculite	water				
2	38	2,98	58,98	1,134	0,27
4	36	3,12	54,64	1,152	0,31
6	34	3,26	52,56	1,188	0,33
8	32	3,46	48,74	1,210	0,35
10	30	3,54	46,78	1,292	0,37
12	28	3,64	45,65	1,312	0,41

By conducting a series of experiments, we selected the composition of the flame retardant composition and selected the optimal number of components in the following ratio (wt.%): vermiculite and orthophosphoric acid - 28, alkali - 26; nitrogen-containing compounds - 12.0; water - 34.0.

To apply the developed flame retardant composition according to the data of tables 1 and 2, we offer

impregnation throughout the entire volume of the material, which makes it possible to control the thickness and uniformity of the coating with a flame retardant solution. At the same time, the existing technological regime, as well as the productivity of the equipment, does not change. The impregnation of the material was carried out using a bath, and a pulverizer through which

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